

Photoelectrochemical disinfection efficiency of WO₃-based photoanodes: Development of multifunctional photoelectrocatalytic materials

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ABSTRACT

Access to safe water is a growing global concern, with millions lacking acceptable water sources. Photocatalysis offers eco-friendly water remediation, yet its combination with electrocatalysis for both water treatment and hydrogen production remain underexplored. This study investigates UVA LED photoelectrocatalysis using WO₃-based photoanodes, alone or in heterojunction with BiVO₄, to purify wastewater and co-produce hydrogen. Tests on polluted water streams containing 10⁵ PFU mL⁻¹ of MS2 bacteriophage virus and 10⁶ CFU mL⁻¹ of *E. coli* reveal that nanostructured WO₃ achieves rapid MS2 disinfection within 5 min. ($k = 0.80 \text{ min}^{-1}$), with enhanced efficiency over flat counterparts. However, nanostructuring does not improve *E. coli* inactivation due to bacterium size constraints. These findings advance the design of tandem photoreactors for dual wastewater purification and energy generation.

1. Introduction

The presence of bacteria and viruses in wastewater, especially following the SARS, MERS, and SARS-CoV-2 pandemics, has raised global health concerns. These pathogens, resilient to environmental conditions, are responsible for waterborne diseases [1]. Traditional wastewater treatments like chlorination and ozonation have been standard, but recent concerns have arisen due to their potential to generate carcinogenic disinfection by-products [2]. With climate change exacerbating water scarcity, the demand for innovative tertiary water treatment methods is pressing, especially amidst the growing reliance on treated wastewater reuse [3–5].

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP), which use photocatalysts to generate *in-situ* highly reactive transitory species capable of converting organic contaminants to harmless by-products, have been explored as alternatives. Inorganic semiconductor systems like TiO₂, ZnO, CuO, and WO₃ are commonly used for their stability and low toxicity. However, these photocatalysts require long-lived photogenerated charge carriers to oxidise water contaminants efficiently [6]. Strategies to minimise

charge carrier recombination have been explored, being the formation of heterojunction systems, such as anatase/rutile TiO₂, Cu₂O/TiO₂, WO₃/TiO₂, and WO₃/BiVO₄, the most effective method to improve charge transport and reduce their recombination [7–11]. Additionally, nanostructuring of heterojunction systems can greatly improve photocatalytic efficiency by separating long light absorption depths and inadequate minority carrier diffusion lengths to enhance charge carrier transport [11–14].

In this work, we investigate the efficiency of flat and nanostructured WO₃, and their combinations with BiVO₄, to eliminate water contaminants using electrocatalysis (EC), photocatalysis (PC), and photoelectrocatalysis (PEC). Previous research has shown that the inactivation of MS2 and *E. coli* under PEC conditions can be achieved using various photocatalytic materials, including TiO₂ [15–17] and WO₃ [18,19]. However, some research groups have found that the choice of supporting electrolyte for inactivation experiments can significantly impact the formation of reactive species and the subsequent photocatalytic efficiency. McMichael *et al.* tested TiO₂ nanotubes with NaCl and Na₂SO₄ electrolytes for PEC inactivation of *E. coli* K12 [16], finding that NaCl led

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to rapid *E. coli* inactivation (5- log (99.999 %)) in 30 min, whilst Na₂SO₄ achieved a 2.51- log (99.61 %) reduction in 180 min. This difference was attributed to the generation of reactive chlorine species in NaCl that were able to contribute to the break down of the bacterium.

Nanostructured WO₃ photoanodes have shown remarkable inactivation rates for both MS2 and *E. coli*. Tolosana-Moranchel *et al.* compared WO₃ and P25 photoanodes, observing that WO₃ achieved 5- log (99.999 %) inactivation of MS2 (initial concentration 10⁷ PFU mL⁻¹) in 6 min compared to 5- log (99.999 %) inactivation within 14 min when P25 was used (1.3 V vs SCE, solar simulator). The higher efficiency of WO₃ was explained in terms of its morphology, which presented a higher ratio of absorbed radiation to incident radiation for their radiation source and reduced electron-hole recombination [18]. Additionally, coupling WO₃ with metal oxides like BiVO₄ can produce highly efficient photocatalytic systems, which have been historically used for energy storage applications [20]. However, some work in water remediation has been conducted with WO₃/BiVO₄ systems. Cristino *et al.* studied the removal of contaminants of emerging concern ketoprofen and levofloxacin [21], finding that both contaminants were oxidised at the WO₃/BiVO₄ interface faster than their single analogues. Another study conducted by Omrani *et al.* was based on the photocatalytic degradation of sulfasalazine using nano-composite WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄, finding a near four-fold improvement in removal efficiency for the heterojunction system [22]. However, despite the wide use of these heterojunction systems for energy storage applications, there is a lack of research on the use of WO₃/BiVO₄ and PEC for water remediation applications.

In this work, we evaluate the implementation of five different photocatalytic materials (flat and nanostructured WO₃, flat BiVO₄, as well as flat and nanostructured WO₃/BiVO₄) for PEC water treatment applications by studying their kinetics and energy efficiency for the removal of model organic (methanol, MeOH), bacterial (*E. coli*) and viral (MS2) species. To understand the impact of voltage bias and light, samples herein are examined with/ without voltage bias (*i.e.* under PEC and PC conditions) and with/ without light (*i.e.* under PEC and EC conditions). The primary aim of this work is to identify the materials and parameters that result in the most effective PEC disinfection of water streams. As hydrogen is co-evolved during PEC operation, the outcomes of this work represent a step forward in the development of multifunctional materials for water treatment and energy storage applications.

2. Experimental

2.1. Photoanode materials

Flat and nanostructured WO₃, BiVO₄, and layered heterojunction systems were synthesised via aerosol-assisted chemical vapour deposition (AACVD). The photocatalytic materials were deposited onto fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates (1.25 × 2.5 cm, TEC 15, Hartford Glass Co.), with the photocatalyst layer covering 2.5 cm². The synthesis of WO₃ was previously reported by Kafizas *et al.* [23]. The same method was used here for the WO₃ and adapted for the synthesis of BiVO₄ by AACVD. Triphenyl bismuth (Alfa Aesar, 98 %) and vanadium (III) acetylacetonate (Aldrich, 97 %) were dissolved in a 3:1 solution of acetone:methanol and transferred with compressed air carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 L min⁻¹ over a substrate heated at 400 °C.

2.2. Physical characterisation

The physical characterisation of flat and nanostructured WO₃ was previously reported by Kafizas *et al.* [23]. In this work, X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were measured on a modified Bruker-AXS D8 diffractometer with parallel beam optics equipped with a PSD LynxEye silicon strip detector. X-rays were generated using a Cu source ($V = 40$ kV, $I = 30$ mA) with Cu K_{α1} ($\lambda = 1.54056$ Å) and Cu K_{α2} ($\lambda = 1.54439$ Å) emitted with an intensity of 2:1. The incident beam was held at 1° with respect to the sample and the angular range of the patterns collected between 6° ≤

$2\theta \leq 70^\circ$ with a step size of 0.034°. The patterns were compared with standards from the Physical Sciences Data-Service, confirming the deposition of BiVO₄ on the FTO and on WO₃ when fabricating heterojunctions as shown in the [Supplementary Information Figure S1](#). The morphology and thicknesses of the WO₃ and BiVO₄ films were studied using a Zeiss Auriga Cross Beam instrument (5 kV, working distance 5.0 nm). To prevent charging, the samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer of chromium (~15 nm). All SEM images of the samples used in this work are shown in the [Supplementary Information Figure S4](#). For the samples tested in this work, the flat WO₃ samples had thicknesses of approximately 400 nm, while the flat BiVO₄ formed with thicknesses of 200 nm. The flat WO₃/BiVO₄ has a 400 nm thick layer of WO₃ and a 400 nm thick layer of BiVO₄. The nanostructured WO₃ formed a layer 2000 nm thick and the BiVO₄ uniformly coats the WO₃ nanoneedles with a radial thickness of 50–100 nm. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of WO₃ nanoneedles and WO₃/BiVO₄ NNS heterojunctions were analysed using a JEOL 2100Plus instrument with Gatan Digital Micrograph software. All TEM and STEM images are shown in the [Supplementary Information \(Figures S5, S6, and S7\)](#). Optical properties and bandgap measurements are shown in [Figure S8](#). Additionally, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses ([Figure S9 and S10](#)) were performed using a Thermo Scientific K-alpha spectrometer with monochromated Al K alpha radiation, a dual beam charge compensation system and constant pass energy of 50 eV. Survey scans were collected in the range of 0–1200 eV. High-resolution peaks were used for the principal peaks of W (4 f), Bi (4 f), V (2p), O (1 s), and C (1 s), which were modelled using sensitivity factors to study the environment of the different elements within the region of analysis (spot size 400 nm).

2.3. Photoelectrochemical cell setup

The experiments were conducted using a solution of 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ and deionised water, sterilised in an autoclave at 121 °C for 21 min. They were carried out in a 50 mL borosilicate cell with a jacket, illuminated by a digitally controlled UVA LED Lamp (365 nm +/- 5 nm at 25 °C, Seoul Viosys UV1000-36, emission range 343 – 400 nm) placed above the cell. A full description of the UVA LED lamp used in this paper can be found elsewhere [24]. The UVA lamp was chosen to provide photons of sufficient energy to photoexcite electrons in both the WO₃ and BiVO₄ materials. The cell has a 1.5 × 2.5 cm opening in its lid to allow light in and was covered by an opaque jacket to prevent light ingress from external sources. The solution was stirred continuously at 200 rpm by a magnetic PTFE stir bar to keep the pollutants evenly distributed. A three-electrode setup was used for photoelectrochemical and electrochemical experiments, with a back-lit photoanode, an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (0.197 V NHE at 298 K, eDAQ), and a platinum mesh counter electrode (2 × 2 cm). To ensure a high degree of photon absorption close to the TCO/photocatalyst interface, irradiation was performed from the back side. The thicker materials are nanostructured allowing for improved migration of charge carriers to the surface. Additionally, the nanostructured photoanodes are porous allowing diffusion of pollutants into the structure. The mesh platinum counterelectrode used in the work reduced the number of photons reaching the photoanode surface significantly, thus choosing back lit conditions would maximise photons reaching the photoanode and being absorbed close to the TCO/photocatalyst surface to reduce charge carrier recombination.

The photoanode and counter electrode were 1.5 cm apart and controlled and monitored by an Autolab potentiostat (µAutolab Type III). Images of the experimental setup can be found in the [Supplementary Information \(Figure S3\)](#). The radiant intensity from the lamp in the cell was determined by ferrioxalate actinometry [25], also shown in the [Supplementary Information \(Figure S4\)](#). Two UVA LED based radiant intensity values were used in this work, 44.7 mW cm⁻² ± 1.19 mW cm⁻² for methanol oxidation and MS2 inactivation, whilst 19.1 mW cm⁻² ± 1.35 mW cm⁻² was used for *E. coli* inactivation, as it

was found from initial tests that the higher radiant intensity value achieved a 5-log (99.999 %) reduction of the *E. coli* within one hour, and thus would be unsuitable to assess the inactivation kinetics of the photocatalytic materials. Tests were conducted under photoelectrocatalytic (UVA lamp on, potential bias applied in closed circuit), electrocatalytic (UVA lamp off, potential bias applied in closed circuit), and photocatalytic (UVA lamp on, no potential bias applied in open circuit). PEC, EC, and PC experiments were repeated in triplicate, with the mean and standard deviation calculated to represent the average and error values, respectively.

2.4. MS2 enumeration

MS2 coliphage (ATCC 15597B1) was used as a model virus for evaluating disinfection kinetics. The inactivation of viable MS2 virus was determined by a double-layer agar method, requiring Tryptone Yeast Glucose (TYG) medium, semi-solid agar, and agar. TYG medium was prepared using 10 g L⁻¹ tryptone (vegetable, Millipore), 1 g L⁻¹ yeast extract (Sigma-Aldrich), and 8 g L⁻¹ NaCl in deionised water. Additionally, 5 g L⁻¹ and 15 g L⁻¹ of agar (Sigma-Aldrich) were added to the medium to prepare semi-solid and solid agar medium, respectively. All solutions were autoclaved at 121 °C for 21 min, after which 10 g L⁻¹ glucose (Sigma Life Sciences), 2.94 g L⁻¹ CaCl₂ (Sigma-Aldrich), and 0.01 g L⁻¹ thiamine (sigma-Aldrich) were added to the solutions when cooled to 50 °C. The bacterial host (*E. coli* C300 171, ATCC 15597) was cultured in TYG medium for 6 h at 37 °C with rotary agitation of 100 rpm prior to enumeration. 1 mL of the bacterial host was then mixed with 0.1 mL of sample (or decimal dilutions using Phosphate Buffer Saline) and 5 mL of melted semi-solid TYG agar. The mixture was then poured onto 100 mm of solid TYG agar dishes and left to air dry in a biological safety cabinet. Solidified plates were inverted and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h before examining for plaques. The detection limit of this method was 2 PFU mL⁻¹. An initial MS2 concentration of 10⁵ PFU mL⁻¹ was used during inactivation experiments.

2.5. *E. coli* enumeration

E. coli K-12 (ATCC 23631) was used as a model bacterium for evaluating the inactivation kinetics. *E. coli* was cultured overnight in Luria Bertani broth (tryptone 10 g L⁻¹, NaCl 10 g L⁻¹ and yeast extract 5 g L⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich) and incubated at 37 °C, with rotary agitation of 100 rpm under aerobic conditions. Bacteria were collected after 20–24 h of incubation, yielding a concentration of 10⁸ CFU mL⁻¹. 1 mL of *E. coli* suspensions was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 25 min, washed three times with 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ solution and diluted to 10⁶ CFU mL⁻¹. The bacterial inactivation was followed by analysing the concentration of viable bacteria in the samples taken throughout the reaction. The quantification was carried out following a standard serial dilution procedure, spotting 10 µl samples of each decimal dilution on 100 mm LB nutrient agar plates and incubating them at 37 °C for 24 h before counting. For reaction times with lower bacteria concentrations, higher volumes (100 mL and 1 mL) of the undiluted suspensions were also plated to reduce the detection limit to 10 CFU mL⁻¹. *E. coli* initial concentrations were 10⁶ CFU mL⁻¹.

2.6. Formaldehyde colorimetry

Methanol was chosen as a model organic pollutant to evaluate the degradation of organic matter. The experimental setup consisted of a supporting electrolyte solution of 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ (Scharlau) containing methanol (Scharlau) with an initial concentration of 0.1 M. Given that methanol is in excess and dissolved oxygen is present in the reaction solution, methanol is selectively oxidised to formaldehyde. Given the excess of methanol in the system, the system can be described by a zero-order kinetic model, as demonstrated previously [26,27]. Thus, the evolution of formaldehyde was followed through Nash's colourimetric

method [25].

2.7. Electrochemical characterisation

Linear sweep voltammetry was conducted on all photoanodes, as well as the blank FTO substrate, for all pollutants in a solution of 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ in darkness and light at a sweep rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ between 0.35 and 1.50 V vs Ag/AgCl. During EC and PEC reactions, chronoamperograms were recorded at a +0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl potential bias. A UVA LED light intensity of 44.7 mW cm⁻² ± 1.19 mW cm⁻² was used for all voltammetry tests regardless of the enhanced inactivation of *E. coli* at this light intensity to compare the photocurrent response between all three pollutants under equivalent conditions.

2.8. Faradaic efficiency calculation

The Faradaic efficiencies of the photoanodes were calculated from the MeOH oxidation experiments, as the known stoichiometry of the conversion of methanol to formaldehyde gives a more accurate value than the calculation using the approximate number of hydroxyl radicals involved in the inactivation of MS2 and *E. coli*. A two-step methanol oxidation mechanism has been previously proposed, where the reaction begins with the adsorption of the methanol molecule to a metal centre, releasing a proton. Then, a surface hole is transferred to the methoxide forming a methoxy radical, which then undergoes a second oxidation step when an electron is injected into the conduction band of the photoanode, producing formaldehyde [28–30]. The proposed mechanism is shown below:

The Faradaic efficiency was calculated by dividing the measured rate of formaldehyde generated by the photocurrent generated from all reactions in the cell [31]:

$$FE(\%) = \frac{CH_2O(\text{mols}^{-1}) \times N_A}{(I_{photo})/e} \quad (1)$$

Where CH₂O is the rate of formation of formaldehyde in the reaction, N_A is the Avogadro's number, I_{photo} is the average photocurrent per second during the formaldehyde formation reaction, and e is the elementary charge constant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Linear sweep voltammetry; PEC and EC performance

The current-voltage characteristics of the WO₃ and BiVO₄ photoanodes were analysed by linear sweep voltammetry, as shown in Fig. 1. All photoanodes containing WO₃ produced photocurrent under irradiation across the tested voltage range for all pollutants examined. It should be noted that under the testing conditions employed there will be competition between the oxidation of water and the pollutant. Importantly, the intermediates that can be formed during the oxidation of water (e.g. hydroxyl radicals, hydrogen peroxide, etc.) may contribute to the indirect oxidation of the pollutants present.

In darkness, an onset in the current was seen at a potential of roughly 1.4–1.45 V vs Ag/AgCl, which is typical for these photoanode materials [32]. Under irradiation, flat BiVO₄ presented an onset potential for all solutions of ~1 V vs Ag/AgCl, whereas all WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄ materials presented onset potentials of 0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl or less. The positive shift in the onset potential of the flat BiVO₄ photoanode is likely caused by the dead layer effect. This effect arises due to the thin layer of BiVO₄

Fig. 1. Current–voltage curves of select photoanodes measured in 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 electrolyte (pH = 6.38), in a mixture of 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 with 0.1 M MeOH, and in a mixture of 10^5 PFU mL^{-1} with 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 for dark (dashed lines) and back irradiation (solid lines) conditions. Photoanodes were irradiated from the back using a 365 nm LED light. The voltage was swept from the cathodic to anodic potentials from 0.35 to 1.5 V_{RHE} (50 mV s^{-1}).

deposited on FTO [33] (shown in the inset of Figure S2(c) of Supplementary Information). It is believed that this mismatch in lattice morphology between the BiVO_4 and FTO leads to the formation of amorphous material close to the interface dense in trap sites [34]. Flat and nanostructured WO_3 materials provide the greatest improvements in photocurrent with the introduction of methanol to the sodium sulphate electrolyte, with methanol acting as a hole scavenger to reduce recombination [35]. Interestingly, the introduction of methanol to the sodium sulphate solution results in a large increase in photocurrent for NNs WO_3 , however a lesser increase is observed for NNs $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ as the valance band holes of the BiVO_4 layer have lower energy than WO_3 to generate hydroxyl radicals from water for methanol oxidation [36, 37]. Another explanation could be that the electron-hole pairs in the $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ heterojunction materials are much longer lived than in WO_3 materials, which increase the rate of water oxidation, a typically slow reaction requiring holes to exist for relatively long periods of time [38, 39]. Another factor is differences in concentration, with water being ~ 550 parts per 1 part of methanol. Therefore, the introduction of methanol to the cell would not be expected to drastically increase the photocurrent produced. Across the range of materials, the voltammetry tests with 10^6 CFU mL^{-1} *E. coli* partially reduced the photocurrent produced compared to the 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 alone. The reduction in photocurrent could be attributed to the large size of *E. coli* bodies blocking sites on the photocatalytic material, a steric hindrance effect, thus reducing the production rate of oxidizing species [40,41]. Similarly, voltammetry measurements with 10^5 PFU mL^{-1} MS2 reduced the photocurrent compared to 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 solutions but to a lesser extent compared to *E. coli*, likely due to the smaller size and lower concentration of MS2 in solution blocking less sites on the photocatalytic surface than *E. coli*.

3.2. Evaluation of the methanol oxidation performance

For reactions including MeOH, the efficiency of MeOH oxidation to formaldehyde was assessed. For PEC and EC tests, samples were held at

an applied potential of 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl. For PEC and PC tests, samples were irradiated with a 365 nm UVA LED light.

Fig. 2 shows the PEC, EC and PC kinetic constants for the oxidation of methanol to formaldehyde. Plots of formaldehyde formation versus time are shown in Supplementary Information (Figure S5). PEC kinetic constants were at least one order of magnitude higher than those found under EC and PC conditions.

When used alone, BiVO_4 suffers from high electron-hole recombination due to the short diffusion lengths of the charge carriers (~ 70 nm) [42]. However, when coupled in a heterojunction with WO_3 , charge carrier diffusion is improved by the offset in band energies and induced electric fields [20]. Higher kinetic constants were seen for nanostructured materials compared to their flat equivalents, which was attributed to the combination of increased material thickness (allowing for higher photon absorption), an increased active surface area available for MeOH oxidation, and a shorter diffusion path through the nanostructured WO_3 for the charge carriers formed [43]. Comparing the nanostructured materials in more detail, the $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ sample showed a lower kinetic constant for MeOH oxidation to formaldehyde than the WO_3 sample (Fig. 2). This was despite the photocurrent being partly higher in the nanostructured $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ sample (Fig. 1). This is attributed to the comparatively lower Faradaic efficiency (calculated from Eq. 1) seen in nanostructured $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ for MeOH oxidation to formaldehyde ($\sim 62\%$) compared with nanostructured WO_3 ($\sim 100\%$). The cause of this lower Faradaic efficiency may be due to changes in selectivity, where a greater preference for water oxidation and/or alternative MeOH oxidation products may be present in the nanostructured $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ sample. It should be noted that the near-zero photocurrent measurements and low formaldehyde production rates for MeOH oxidation on flat BiVO_4 photoanodes gave Faradaic efficiencies with error values greater than 100%, and therefore, were not included.

In ascending order, the Faradaic efficiencies (shown in Fig. 2) of the photoanodes are flat $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4 < \text{flat } \text{WO}_3 < \text{NNs } \text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4 < \text{NNs } \text{WO}_3$. Interestingly, these Faradaic efficiencies closely followed the

Fig. 2. Comparison of the oxidation of methanol to formaldehyde kinetic constants using photoelectrocatalytic (PEC), electrocatalytic (EC), and photocatalytic (PC) conditions. Table S1 in the Supplementary Information gives the numerical value of all rate constants. In all experiments, a 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ solution was used as electrolyte with an initial concentration of MeOH of 0.1 M. A 365 nm LED light was used for the PEC and PC experiments under back lit conditions. An applied voltage of 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl was used for the PEC and EC experiments.

observed trends in the kinetic constants for MeOH oxidation to formaldehyde.

This effect is mainly due to the degradation mechanism of methanol, where hydroxyl groups play an important role in the oxidation of MeOH to formaldehyde. The diffusion paths for hydroxyl radicals are shorter in nanostructured materials. However, nanostructured WO₃/BiVO₄ heterojunctions present a lower rate of generation of hydroxyl radicals due to the promotion of electrons from the BiVO₄ layer [44]. Therefore, pristine nanostructured WO₃ showed higher rates for the degradation of MeOH followed by its heterojunction analogue.

3.3. Evaluation of the MS2 inactivation efficiency

The antiviral efficiency of the photocatalytic materials studied in this work was evaluated through the inactivation of the MS2 bacteriophage. MS2 concentration versus time plots for the five photoanodes are shown in Supplementary Information (Figure S6). These antiviral properties were examined under PEC, EC, and PC conditions. The inactivation of MS2 can be fitted to a pseudo-first order kinetic expression using the gradient of the slope of the log inactivation of MS2 versus time [45]. PEC conditions showed higher efficiency by nearly one order of magnitude (Fig. 3). Interestingly, PEC inactivation of MS2 showed more comparable inactivation rates for flat (WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄) photoanodes, with a 4-log (99.99%) inactivation within 5 min, and nanostructured (WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄) photoanodes, with a 5-log (99.999%) inactivation within 5 min than was observed for the methanol oxidation. Comparing the respective flat and nanostructured materials, the kinetic constants

for MS2 inactivation for the nanostructured materials was only 30–40% higher than their flat equivalents (Fig. 3), whereas for MeOH this value was closer to 10 times larger (Fig. 2). This may be due to the near 40-fold difference in size between MeOH and MS2. MeOH has an effective diameter of ~0.6 nm, whilst MS2 has a diameter of ~23 nm, therefore, MeOH will likely be able to better penetrate the gaps between nanostructures. Thus, the larger surface area afforded by the nanostructured materials is less beneficial to MS2 than it is to MeOH. Notably, all WO₃ containing samples studied herein showed high MS2 inactivation rates, irrespective of material geometry.

It has been shown in the literature that the inactivation of MS2 is mainly associated with surface generated hydroxyl radicals and some direct oxidation at holes [15]. The negatively charged capsid of MS2 is electrostatically attracted to the positively charged photoanode surface, thus improving the oxidation pathway of MS2 by •OH. The generation of •OH is typically slower on BiVO₄ than WO₃ photocatalysts, with water oxidation on BiVO₄ progressing via multiple proton-couple electron transfer reaction pathways [46]. Furthermore, WO₃ materials have a valence band of 3.1 eV at pH 0, whilst BiVO₄ has a valence band of 2.4 eV at pH 0 [36]. The overpotential required to produce •OH from water is 2.7 eV at pH 0 [37], indicating that WO₃ would be expected to generate more •OH under the same conditions, and may explain why all the WO₃ containing materials studied herein displayed high MS2 inactivation rates.

Tolosana-Moranchel *et al.* achieved high photoelectrocatalytic inactivation rates of MS2 using similar materials. The time taken to reach 5-log (99.999%) inactivation by WO₃ photoanodes tested by

Fig. 3. Kinetic constants of the photoelectrocatalytic (grey bars), electrocatalytic (green bars), and photocatalytic (blue bars) inactivation of MS2 bacteriophage. Table S1 in the Supplementary Information gives the numerical value of all rate constants. In all experiments, a 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ solution was used as electrolyte. A 365 nm LED light was used for the photoelectrocatalytic and photocatalytic experiments under back lit conditions. An applied voltage of 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl was used for the photoelectrocatalytic and electrocatalytic experiments.

Tolosana-Moranchel *et al.* was 6 min (0.89 min⁻¹) [18], whilst the kinetic constant observed in this work for nanostructured WO₃/BiVO₄ was 0.80 min⁻¹ (4.0- log (99.99 %) reduction after 5 min) and 0.75 min⁻¹ (3.84- log (99.986 %) reduction after 5 min) for WO₃ in nanostructured form. The work in this publication uses a higher light intensity and a lower potential bias than the tests conducted by Tolosana-Moranchel *et al.*, which could account for the slightly lower kinetic constants observed in this work as higher potential biases would be expected to improve inactivation rates due to greater electrostatic attraction, lower electron-hole recombination, and the subsequent increased rate of generation of ROS.

3.4. Incident photon to current efficiency

The incidence photon to current efficiency (IPCE) of the photoanodes was calculated using chronoamperometric data from the MS2 inactivation and MeOH oxidation experiments and shown in Fig. 4.

$$IPCE(\%) = \frac{I_{pc}}{e} \frac{c}{P_{in}} \frac{h}{\lambda} \quad (2)$$

Where, I_{pc} is the measured photocurrent, c is the speed of light, h is Planck's constant, e is the elementary charge, P_{in} is the light power and λ is the wavelength.

The highest IPCE value for MS2 inactivation was observed using the flat WO₃/BiVO₄ photoanode, where the WO₃ layer allowed for greater transmission of photons to the BiVO₄, as well as good electron transport back through the WO₃ to the FTO substrate layer. The increased IPCE of flat WO₃/BiVO₄ suggests water oxidation is causing the high photocurrent, as this material did not demonstrate comparatively high MS2 inactivation rates. Although electron transport is improved in nanostructured WO₃ materials [47,48], the layer thickness of the nanostructured WO₃ (shown in Figure S2 of the Supplementary Information)

Fig. 4. Incident photon to current efficiency (IPCE), measured at an applied potential of 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl under back irradiation for the flat (WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄) and nanostructured (WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄) photocatalytic materials evaluated in this work. The IPCE values were obtained from the MS2 inactivation and MeOH oxidation experiments.

combined with the quantum confinement effect due to the increased particle size of nanostructured WO_3 reduces the transmission of photons to the outer tips of the WO_3 needles, where the majority of MS2 inactivation will occur [49].

In the case of MeOH oxidation, the nanostructured WO_3 and $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ photoanodes displayed higher IPCE values than their flat equivalents. This effect is due to the much larger surface-to-volume ratio of the nanostructured photoanodes compared to their flat analogues, thus the comparatively small MeOH molecule can access sites for oxidation throughout the structure. The current doubling effect of MeOH is evident in the nanostructured photoanodes but not in the flat materials. The absolute IPCE values reported in this work are lower than in other publications of the same materials [18]. This is largely due to the low potential bias (0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl) applied to the photoanodes in the experiments to negate the electroosmotic repulsion of negatively charged *E. coli* and MS2 with increasing potential [15,16]. *E. coli* K12 was omitted from IPCE calculations, as the lower light intensity used compared to the other pollutants would not allow for drawing comparisons between all three pollutants as the effect of light intensity on photocatalytic kinetic constants is non-linear [50].

The applied bias photon-to-current efficiency (ABPE) was calculated for methanol oxidation experiments, with the values for the photoanodes shown in Table S2 of the Supplementary Information of this paper and the equation used shown in Eq. S1. The highest ABPE value was observed for the nanostructured materials (NNs $\text{WO}_3=1.66\%$, NNs

$\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4=1.57\%$), whilst the flat materials had ABPE values less than 1 %.

3.5. Evaluation of the *E. coli* inactivation efficiency

The antimicrobial performance of the flat and nanostructured photoanodes investigated in this work was evaluated by comparing the kinetic constants for *E. coli* inactivation. These values were calculated using a non-linear regression algorithm to fit the inactivation curves, as previously detailed by some authors of this work [51].

It can be seen in Fig. 5f that the photocatalytic kinetic constants for the inactivation of *E. coli* showed that the flat $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ photoanode achieved a similar rate of inactivation compared to its flat analogue and the nanostructured photoanodes. To understand this, the size of an *E. coli* bacterium should be considered. *E. coli* is a rod-shaped body of significantly larger dimensions (diameter of 1 μm and length of 2 μm) than MeOH ($\sim 0.6\text{ nm}$) and MS2 bacteriophage ($\sim 23\text{ nm}$). Therefore, the *E. coli* bacterium can only access the upper most layer of the surface of the photoanode. It has been previously reported that a flat WO_3 coating, with a 100 nm thickness, can absorb 45 % of the photons contained in a light source with a 355 nm wavelength, whilst 15 % are absorbed when the irradiating source presents a 400 nm wavelength [52]. In this work, an LED device with a emission range within 343 – 400 nm and a wavelength peak at 367 nm (Figure S7) was used. The photoanodes explored in this work consisted of flat WO_3 layers with a

Fig. 5. a-e) Photoelectrocatalytic (grey squares), electrocatalytic (green circles) and photocatalytic (blue triangles) inactivation of *E. coli* K12 (10^6 CFU mL^{-1} , 50 mL). f) Kinetic constants of the photoelectrocatalytic (grey bars), electrocatalytic (green bars), and photocatalytic (blue bars) inactivation of *E. coli* K12. Table S1 in the Supplementary Information gives the numerical value of all rate constants. In all experiments, a 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 solution was used as electrolyte. A UVA LED light ($19.1\text{ mW cm}^{-2} \pm 1.35\text{ mW cm}^{-2}$) was used for the photoelectrocatalytic and photocatalytic experiments under back lit conditions. An applied voltage of 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl was used for the photoelectrocatalytic and electrocatalytic experiments. Control experiments shown in Supplementary Information (Fig. S8).

thickness of 90 nm, and nanostructured WO₃ layers with a ~3.3 μm thickness. Therefore, as samples were irradiated from the back, a significant portion of the photons are not absorbed by the BiVO₄ layer in heterojunction samples.

PEC inactivation of *E. coli* showed that photoanodes composed of a single layer of nanostructured WO₃ achieved inactivation rates higher than their heterojunction analogues. These results could be attributed to a larger number of hydroxyl radicals being generated in WO₃ photoanodes. Whilst the inactivation of MS2 is largely associated with surface bound •OH, *E. coli* inactivation is associated with a wide variety of ROS, including surface and free •OH, O₂[•], H₂O₂ [53], as well as electrolyte-specific oxidants such as sulphate radicals [54]. WO₃ has a deep valence band associated with the generation of •OH radicals. However, BiVO₄ has band positions able to generate other ROS, such as H₂O₂ and O₂[•] [55]. Nevertheless, •OH has the strongest oxidising potential of the radicals generated by each material. As previously mentioned, nanostructured WO₃ exhibited the highest MeOH oxidation rate under PEC conditions, which is an indication of high h⁺ and •OH generation. It has been shown that H₂O₂ is generated in photoelectrocatalytic WO₃ systems but is unlikely to be the primary ROS responsible for *E. coli* inactivation. This was demonstrated by isolating the generation of H₂O₂ at the cathode and measuring the inactivation of *E. coli*, which was negligible over the duration of the experiment [56]. The authors suggested *E. coli* inactivation was associated with h⁺ generation at the anode. These findings are supported by the poor performance shown by flat BiVO₄ photoanodes, which displayed only a 1- log (90 %) reduction after 30 min for *E. coli* inactivation tests. These results indicate that other ROS may be generated by flat BiVO₄, such as H₂O₂ and O₂[•], which can inactivate *E. coli*, but are less effective at oxidising MS2. Another explanation for the lower activity of the flat and nanostructured WO₃/BiVO₄ photoanodes compared to nanostructured WO₃ could be the formation of an electroosmotic layer. WO₃/BiVO₄ heterojunctions led into a high concentration of holes in the BiVO₄ layer. The SO₄²⁻ ions are attracted to the holes on the BiVO₄ layer, forming an osmotic barrier for the *E. coli* to access sites for inactivation, as observed in previous works [15,16]. In the case of MS2, the smaller size allows for faster diffusion through the osmotic barrier than *E. coli*, thus is not negatively impacted by the high concentration of ions. Another consideration for the poor performance of the nanostructured WO₃/BiVO₄ compared to nanostructured WO₃ is the charge carrier recombination due to hole decay under UVA radiation. Grigioni *et al.* demonstrated that whilst the lifetime of photogenerated holes is improved in WO₃/BiVO₄ systems compared to WO₃ in the visible range (470 nm), at 387 nm the incorporation of BiVO₄ increased hole decay and charge carrier recombination, which could further explain the poor performance of the heterojunction materials compared to WO₃ alone [57].

4. Conclusions

This work explores the use of nanostructured WO₃-based photocatalysts for water disinfection applications using different electrochemical and photocatalytic conditions. Under photoelectrochemical (PEC) conditions, all nanostructured WO₃-containing materials exhibited high rates of inactivation for MS2, *E. coli*, and MeOH oxidation, highlighting their potential for water disinfection applications. This enhanced performance can be attributed to increased photon absorption, active surface area, and improved charge carrier diffusion, although some challenges, such as charge carrier recombination and electroosmotic effects, were observed.

In addition, incident photon to current efficiency (IPCE) showed enhanced performance for nanostructured materials due to their larger surface-to-volume ratio. This work provides valuable insights into the design and optimisation of photocatalytic materials for efficient water disinfection, paving the way for developing multifunctional materials capable of addressing both water treatment and energy storage

challenges.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Javier Marugan: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Cristina Pablos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Anna Hankin:** Writing – review & editing. **George Creasey:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Carlos Sotelo-Vazquez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Conor Reddick:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Simon Stanley:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ken Reynolds:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Andreas Kafizas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Brian Tam:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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This Special Issue is dedicated to honor the retirement of Prof. Santiago Esplugas at the Universitat de Barcelona (UB, Spain), a key figure in the area of Catalytic Advanced Oxidation Processes that has significantly influenced the research and vision of AOP.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2024.114783](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2024.114783).

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